

Enhancing Road Safety: Advanced Traffic Sign Recognition Using Convolutional Neural Networks

1st Hassan Ali Alzayer[†]
Department of Computer Science
College of Computer Science and
Information Technology,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal
University
Dammam 31441, Saudi Arabia
eng.halzayer@gmail.com

2nd Hassan Dhaiman Al Saquor[†]
Department of Computer Science
College of Computer Science and
Information Technology,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal
University
Dammam 31441, Saudi Arabia
hassanAlsaquor@hotmail.com

3rd Ryan Abdullatif Aldoghan[†]
Department of Computer Science
College of Computer Science and
Information Technology,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal
University
Dammam 31441, Saudi Arabia
Ryanoh.ko@hotmail.com

4th Khaled Hussain Almalki[†]
Department of Computer Engineering
College of Computer Science and
Information Technology,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal
University
Dammam 31441, Saudi Arabia
khaledalmalki788@gmail.com

5th Dr. Yasser AlGuwaifli
Department of Computer Science
College of Computer Science and
Information Technology,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal
University
Dammam 31441, Saudi Arabia
ymAlguwaifli@iau.edu.sa

Abstract— This article focuses on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) that can help recognize traffic signs for automated driving and their importance in improving traffic safety. This study involves training a CNN model that will be used in identifying and categorizing traffic signs to ensure effective communication between the road environment, as well as driver-operated and autonomous vehicles. The efficiency of advanced threading techniques for data processing and the models' effectiveness is also investigated in the study. This study revealed a great prospect that is hidden in CNN traffic sign recognition, thus contributing to the development of advanced autonomous driving systems. It is concluded that these model prototypes are ready for redesign to improve on them considering the dynamic nature of traffic conditions and recent developments in vehicle automation technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traffic signs are important signposts within road systems and help to ensure safe and efficient transport. It is of great importance because they play a significant role in communication between the road environment and its users. Nevertheless, the meanings of these signs are not exactly alike between a driver and a non-driver resulting in variations in road security. In research conducted in Metro Manila, this difference was observed especially about signal recognitions between children belonging to different SES groups [1]. Accuracy and speed in traffic sign recognition is a crucial issue that has gained relevance in such a tech-driven space as automated driving. For ease of navigating, it is vital that automated vehicles should interpret correct reading of these signs. With increasing traffic congestion as cities grow up one can say that making sure drivers can understand and decoded

traffic signs is important in reducing road accidents as well as good traffic flow.

II. BACKGROUND

Traffic sign recognition is a key concern in various research aimed at enhancing road security. As shown in a study in Metro Manila, this explains why traffic signs must be universally understandable among both drivers and non-drivers [1]. That is particularly relevant in the context of automatic driver systems, which involve the juxtaposition of high-tech sensors, AI and ordinary roads constructed for sensory perception by humans [2]. Retro-reflectivity is also an important factor in the visibility and quality of traffic signs that has been reported in a Swedish research study concerning the traffic sign retro reflectivity [3]. These warning signals may not be clearly visible and in some instances, they are not properly maintained, causing a huge danger to road users. A pioneer moved toward preventive maintenance and safer urban roads by employing new machine learning approaches based on deep neural networks for predicting the degradation of the road signs' reflectivity. Moreover, adoption of systems like ROADLANE manifests progresses of Road Lane marking recognition. The utilization of such systems involves advanced digital cameras and innovative computer vision algorithms that translate pertinent roads characteristics relevant for contemporary driver aid software [5].

III. METHODOLOGY

Data Collection and Preparation: We began by collecting 2793 pictures that represented 58 types of road-traffic signs. Therefore, this extensive set of data was carefully selected and

aimed at replicating different types of road sign situations. Each of these images has been very carefully preprocessed such that it has been scaled to same dimension and normalized to make a consistent dataset. Without this preliminary stage, the CNN training could not have been successful.

CNN Model Design and Training: Our study focused around building and deploying a CNN model as its focal point. We designed our model to be efficient in recognizing multiple types of traffic signs such as speed limits, warning or prohibition signs. Then we started the training phase where we used our dataset coupled with sophisticated algorithms that provided an efficient learning procedure. In addition, the model went through several training epochs, while careful observation and changes were made for better understanding by the model.

Threading Techniques in Data Processing: We used complex threading to avoid having unprotected data race while we process our data. Critical sections, atomics' operations, and reductions were among other things used in this process. The above methods were instrumental in controlling concurrent data to make the training phases of the CNN reliable and accurate.

IV. LECTURE REVIEW

A. Road Infrastructure Challenges Faced by Automated Driving :

In this viewpoint, a review paper considers the crossing point between automatic driving technology, traffic control and road structure. This highlights that automated driving does not only involve sensor technology and AI but rather on the road infrastructure that historically has been catering for human perceptions. This paper analyzes the shortcomings and progress in automated driving technology focusing on the roads. It emphasizes, among others, on international harmonization of traffic signs and road markings, road infrastructure maintenance, common design patterns, digitization of road networks, and necessity of interdisciplinary collaboration to address these and other issues in order to achieve better results. Such areas are vital in the shift from human controlled to autonomous vehicles pointing out to an integrated approach that takes into account changing patterns of road use and technology [3].

B. An Analysis of the Factors Influencing the Retroreflectivity Performance of In-Service Road Traffic Signs:

Retroreflectivity of road traffic signs is an important factor of safety of any road. The study points out Sweden's lack of organized road sign maintenance and inventory program. This study seeks to determine an easy, secure, and appropriate technique that does not involve usage of specialized testing devices in evaluating sign retroreflectivity. The study utilizes two datasets and uses logarithmic regression models to examine factors influencing reflectivity, including age, direction, GPS location, color, and type of road sign. The results pose a great significance when it comes to the safety precautions in regards to the maintenance and management of traffic and traffic signs. Some Common Mistakes.

C. Predicting Traffic Sign Retro-Reflectivity Degradation Using Deep Neural Networks :

Accordingly, this study introduces a state-of-the-art procedure for prognosticating traffic sign retro-reflectivity with the help of deep neural networks. Poor visibility of traffic signs may pose a danger on the roads and cause accidents. The development of this model seeks to help officials plan more efficiently for renewal and repair work. Data for model training was collected from different traffic signs in mind of sheet types, colors, orientation angles as well as aging. In this study, a sensitivity analysis using features showed significant impact of sheeting colors and observational angles, while sign orientation had a less significant effect. Results showed that neural network approach was effective in forecasting retro-reflectivity and can improve traffic safety/cost efficiency [4].

D. The Modular Framework to Support Recognition Algorithms of Road Lane Markings :

modular algorithmic framework developed in this paper, which supports algorithms for recognizing road lane marking that are needed by currently existing driver-assistance systems. This approach relies on frontal digital cameras in cars as well as computer vision techniques applied to determine in situ road features. It incorporates a three-layer approach: pre-processing, processing, and post-processing. Buffering plus RANSAC are used for lane marking recognition. It is possible to adapt this framework into a system that could identify and read other road stuff. Then, these results may add up into advanced safety equipment for vehicles like lane departing warnings [5].

V. RESULT

The use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in traffic sign recognition has been very effective and this is based on the outputs of a recent study that we conducted. The performance of our model was very satisfactory as it could recognize many different signals with an amazing rate of training accuracy score of 97.3 %, validity accuracy score as 86.7 % and accuracy score for test data as 84.77 %. Our data was prepared with utmost care; it involved 2793 images and 58 categories of traffic signs where every single image had been rescaled and normalized for uniformity. Furthermore, the experiment also used advanced techniques threading in order to well deal with races in data processing. Some of the techniques that were utilized included use of critical sections, atomic operations, and reductions for precise handling of data. Importantly, the model showed marked improvement across different epochs as illustrated through our accuracy graph. The constant progression illustrates the effectiveness of this model in learning and adapting over time by improving its classification skills day by day. The minor difference between the training, validating and test accuracies hints at some amount of overfitting. However, it is evident that the system learned well to be able to generalize when encountering new information. The results, therefore, show that CNNs can be relevant in traffic sign recognition, thus indicating areas that require modification prior to actual implementation and opening yet another window for further developments in the technology sector.

VI. ANALYSIS

Various execution time measurements for every method of threading were reported in detail showing their individual efficiency. The critical section method normally took the most amount of time making it the least efficient technique for this application. However, the two other approaches of reduction and atomic operations showed significantly better efficiency. Reduction method stood out among others due to the speed and it increased even more with growing number of cores. This affirms that when it comes to multi-core processing, the reduction approach offers better scalability options, resulting into huge performance advantages especially on high concurrent scenarios. Atomic operations are another good case, which together with complexity give a harmony with execution time. The analysis culminates in a crucial conclusion: choosing one synchronization method over the other in multi-threaded programming is highly determinant on performance. While designing parallel algorithms, this is one of the factors that should be handled cautiously lest efficiency remains wanting.

The second set seems to consist of several instances of “speed limit (5 km/ h)”, depicted differently, possibly involving various phases of learning within a CNN. Some of these signs include “Children crossing” and “Don’t go left or right”, which are intermittently featured in this series and probably show the progression steps a CNN goes through before it can understand to identify and classify these directives. This implies that both assemblages are considered illustrations of intricate operations that one goes through when training a CNN to identify several kinds of traffic signs which may be used in autonomous vehicles driving or advanced driver assistance systems.

Figure 1 Traffic Signs

The first group of images have traffic signs which may include directions such as “Go right” and prohibition like “don’t go left”. There are also warning signs like “watch out for cars” and speed limits ranging from “speed limit 15 km” to “speed limit 80”

Figure 3 Speed limit 5

It seems to be a heatmap or thermal image representation of a “Speed limit (5 km/h)” traffic sign probably derived from an analytical or feature visualization of machine learning model e.g., convolution neural network (CNN). This type of heatmap is usually employed to showcase where the neural network pays attention to when deciding such as this one for number recognition from a road sign. Color generally has a connotation of coolness to warmth and the intensity of activity within the model. It will also assist researchers and engineers comprehend how the model is perceiving the characteristics of the sign and that may be important in correcting and further enhancing the model output.

Figure 2 Traffic Signs 2

Figure 4 Accuracy Graph

Accuracy Graph: Plot of the CNN performance over epoch, where the x axis is the epoch, and the y presents the per cent accuracy on training data. Normally, the curve would start climbing upwards and then level out showing learning and final stability for the modeling.

Figure 6 Performance of Different Synchronization Techniques

This output is typically used to measure the performance of different synchronization techniques in a parallel computing environment. The "Critical Section" method might be using the critical directive of OpenMP, ensuring exclusive access to a section of code. The "Atomic Operation" likely uses the atomic directive for individual memory updates that must be atomic. The "Reduction" method uses the reduction directive to combine variables from all threads into a single, final value. The execution times are quite close, with the "Atomic Operation" being the fastest and the "Critical Section" the slowest. However, all methods seem to handle the same amount of data traffic and work on the same number of labels, suggesting a controlled environment to measure just the overhead of synchronization.

Figure 5 Set of Performance Testing Results

The image displays a set of performance testing results for various threading methods across different numbers of processor cores. It specifically measures the time taken for tasks using critical sections, reduction, and atomic operations. The data suggests that as the number of cores increases, the time efficiency of reduction and atomic operations improves, outperforming the critical section method. This information is valuable for optimizing parallel processing tasks in software development.

VII. DISCUSSION

Regarding this article discussion on the traffic sign recognition's results, we will commence highlighting some crucial findings and go ahead with exploring the implications and possible issues for further study or optimization.

Key Findings:

- The Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) employed in the project achieved high accuracy rates: Training (97.3%), validation (86.7%) and test (84.77%). It shows that CNNs work when it comes to recognizing traffic signs.
- During dataset preparation, 2793 images were subjected to careful processing within 58 categories, all of which underwent rescaling and normalization making it even more suitable for use by the algorithm and as such, it performed quite well.
- Processing of data was done efficiently through the use of advanced threading techniques like critical sections, atomic operations, and reductions.

- The accuracy chart improved evenly through epochs showing that the model learned and adapted to classify properly as epochs progressed.
- Performance testing of threading approaches showed that the reduction approach and atomic operation had better scale than critical sections as they were more appropriate in multi-core processing environments.

Implications:

- The high accuracy rates indicate that the model possesses the ability to identify traffic signs, which bodes well for autonomous vehicles as well as ADAS (advanced driver assistance systems).
- A narrow difference among the train, validation, and test accuracies implies over-training that may be corrected during subsequent versions of the modeling process by enhancing the model's performance on new data.
- Threading techniques and performance considerations for selecting appropriate synchronization algorithms show the necessity of making an optimal choice of synchronization methods in case one is developing a multi-threaded program which should be maximally productive.

Areas for Improvement and Further Research:

- Some of the methods that are worth of consideration to counter this problem could include the use of dropout, regularization, and larger datasets having diverse images.
- It is worth mentioning that increasing accuracy further by modifying different CNN architectures or hyperparameters would also be a valid option.
- Other aspects that deserve consideration include the effect of image preprocessing techniques such as Gamma correction and contrast limited histogram equalization among others.
- To ensure that the model performs well during different weather and lightings, it could be tested under such changing conditions.
- Using lightweight CNN architectures during investigation may be a consideration for resource constrained applications.

To sum it up, As can be seen, the outcomes of this project are extremely promising, proving that CNNs have great potential for automated traffic sign detection. However, the model was able to perform excellently although improvements are still

needed on the generalization as well as multithreading aspect. The model may be further studied and tested in diverse road conditions in future work.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This final report demonstrates that CNNs are effective in traffic sign recognition. It shows important steps in road safety and automated cars. Accuracy rate is quite high, which proves an ability of the CNNs to distinguish and identify traffic signs. Excessive overfitting points to the need for optimization, which is what this project shows. Specifically, the importance of modern computation and artificial intelligence for sophisticated traffic sign detection. Enhancements on the way can concern diversity of data sets, various CNN architectures and adaptation of the model on changing environment conditions. Not just a research contribution in computer science, this project will help design the safest possible systems for automated cars. In addition, the results and procedures used here point to future work that must be carried out as well as stressing the significance of perpetual progress at this juncture of technology and road security.

IX. REFERENCES

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